

SERVANT LEADERSHIP, MOTIVATION AND MORAL HAZARD

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to assess the potential effects of motivation and servant leadership on moral hazard in the workplace, particularly among Indonesian teachers. This influence phenomenon is connected to stewardship theory in Indonesian education, where moral hazard behaviour is still present among instructors despite Eastern culture's emphasis on subordinates' loyalty to superiors. The goal of this research is to provide readers with a thorough grasp of how moral hazard may be minimised via the use of motivation and servant leadership. Four hundred teachers in Wonosobo Regency participated in the quantitative study design. The analysis's findings demonstrate that moral hazard is favourably and substantially influenced by motivation and servant leadership. With its emphasis on service, servant leadership fosters a moral and responsible work environment, and incentive serves as a deterrent by lowering dishonest behaviour and fraud. The moral hazard issue is brought up by the conflict of interest between the principal (teacher) and the agent (principal), according to the agency theory viewpoint. Because of the school principal's accountability as well as intrinsic and extrinsic incentives, teachers often engage in morally dubious behaviour. In conclusion, by highlighting the benefits of servant leadership and motivation as a means of fostering an ethical and responsible work environment, this study significantly advances our knowledge of and response to the issue of moral hazard in Indonesian educational settings. This has a bearing on raising academic standards, learning quality, and the integrity of the educational process overall.

Keywords: Moral Hazard, Motivation, Indonesian Education, Servant leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Background

The term used to describe when people spend more than they should only because they can get insurance is "moral hazard." (Marshall, 1976). As a result, the beneficiary continues to spend even when his benefit margin is less than the insured cost since he continues to get purchase subsidies. This perspective on moral hazard is intriguing and calls for further investigation. As stated in the health insurance book written by (cmptm, 2006) A person's moral hazard occurs when their reputation, character, network, lifestyle, financial obligations, and environment influence their conduct while executing an insurance contract.

Afterwards, moral hazard is used by several domains, including economics, politics, and finance. There is a "moral hazard" when someone is pressured by (Arnott & Stiglitz, 1988). The question of whether or whether moral considerations could impact human motivation is central to moral psychology. Using a moral argument is one way to create a case for doing something. When one party decides to take a chance, even if another party might wind up paying the price, we have a moral hazard scenario (Yang, 2016).

Despite its Eastern cultural leanings, which emphasise superior-subordinate respect, moral hazard is linked to stewardship theory in Indonesia, particularly in the educational sector. More research is needed in Indonesia on the subject of moral hazard behaviour in the workplace. Finding answers and encouraging more employee responsibility requires a deeper understanding of moral hazard in the Indonesian context, which in turn requires knowledge of the elements that impact this conduct in the classroom.

Moral hazard in the workplace has the potential to negatively impact students' academic performance, the quality of their learning, their professionalism, and their ethics on the job. Laziness has the potential to lower classroom performance and job efficiency. The absence of repercussions for one's activities may lead to a decline in individual motivation at work, a compromise in the integrity of the educational process, and an encouragement of risk-taking and rule-breaking. If educators really want their pupils to learn more effectively, they must establish higher standards for them.

The instructor has an impact on the students' performance level. Educators should conduct themselves ethically at all times, as it is a professional responsibility. The bedrock of ethical conduct in the educational setting is transparency, candour, and participation from all students (Silahuddin, 2016). Integral to this code of ethics are the moral principles that outline the proper and improper ways in which a teacher should lead, guide, educate, train, assess, and evaluate students (Gade, 2015)

A worker's employment contract is based on two parts of their work: the procedure and the output. An individual's performance is evaluated using the outcomes-based approach, which centres on the results that they accomplish while working. The term "outcomes-based" is used to describe the objectives that workers are expected to achieve by a certain date. In contrast, process-based performance assessments give more credit to an employee's actual work performance.

Goals in work stress the significance of employees following procedures and doing their jobs well. Evaluate how well you conducted on the job. Monitoring job quality, standard compliance, and careful observation are all examples of process-based methods. A process-based evaluation relies on the candidate's demonstrated competence in efficiently and consistently completing assigned tasks according to predetermined procedures. One possible outcome of this approach is an indication of whether or not instructors are capable of carrying out their duties to the required level.

Staff members' adherence to policy and procedure may improve under a leader with a servant leadership style. Assisting subordinates in realizing their full potential is the priority of a servant-leader. Staff morale and compliance with policies might both improve as a result. Leaders may inspire their teams to achieve more by adopting this style of leadership, which emphasizes showing appreciation and assisting.

In addition, managers who lead with a servant mentality will make sure their employees know how to follow protocols. Hence, if you need help getting individuals to adhere strictly to protocols, servant leadership might be the way to go. A successful leadership strategy that seeks

to fulfil the needs of people while simultaneously cultivating a feeling of community and respect for human dignity in companies and groups is known as servant leadership.

According to research conducted by (Handoyo, 2010), an alternative to leadership in education is servant leadership. This study shows that using the servant leadership style's aspects is crucial, particularly in the areas of wisdom, organisational leadership, and service. Based on servant leadership theory, (Kaltiainen & Hakanen, 2022) servant leadership has the potential to reduce moral hazard conduct, so goes the theory. However, the concept of moral hazard stems from agency theory, which posits that it may happen when a principal is unable to closely monitor an agent's actions and the agent's self-interests cause him to prioritise his aims above the principal's (Petersen, 1993)

When instructors engage in moral hazard behaviour on school property, the principle or other administration should speak with them about it. Anxieties in the classroom may be observed and evaluated in this manner. It is possible to reduce moral hazard for educators by taking the correct steps. Unit heads of educational institutions, notably principals, have the power to execute innovative ideas and tactics to enhance education via the execution of school programmes.

The leader chosen to run the school has the responsibility of creating and enhancing an exceptional education. Those in charge, who also determine the priorities of the country and the state, have a say in the educational system's destiny. They are mostly accountable for enhancing the calibre of human resources in order to make the country more competitive globally (Fernando and Haryani, 2021).

When given instructions, agents often perform the opposite of what their principals intend, according to moral hazard theory. This goes against the grain of Eastern values, as followership is ingrained in Indonesian society. Therefore, stewardship theory and agency theory, both with real-world implications in Indonesian schools, are fundamentally at odds with one another. In order to address the ongoing problem of moral hazard behaviour in educational institutions, this study will provide a servant leadership approach that is in line with the proposal made by (Kaltiainen & Hakanen, 2022). Consequently, the moral hazard problem is seen to be amenable to this servant leadership style.

Based on the theory that this idea has been studied in depth (Kaltiainen & Hakanen, 2022) when it comes to servant leadership specifically, according to this notion, moral hazard might be lessened by servant leadership. However, the agency theory dispute in Indonesia stems from interviews with regional organisations and department heads in Wonosobo Regency, which does not have the authority to directly oversee civil servant instructors. The principal principal, this being the school principal, has yet to learn what the teachers' actual talents are since the civil servant teacher recruiting system has solely employed written examinations thus far. The asymmetric information agency problem is at play here as well. As a result, the problem of moral hazard in government service instruction comes up.

Despite efforts to address the issue, researchers in Wonosobo Regency found that moral hazard behaviour complaints related to PNS punishment were still common in 2023. Since moral hazard has the potential to damage public finances and slow growth, the government is understandably worried about it. As a result, the government must take appropriate action to stop its officials from acting unethically.

Both proactive measures, such as providing incentives and compensation in addition to an appropriate leadership style, and reactive measures, such as strictly enforcing laws, are within the realm of possibility. Also, lower-level supervision, like the school principals, requires its completion as quickly as feasible. People working for the government are expected to perform better if moral hazard conduct is reduced in this way.

In 2023, researchers collected and examined field data from elementary schools (SD) in the form of permission, attendance, and teacher attendance records. Many employees in Wonosobo Regency continued to be chronically tardy, leave early, or not show up for roll calls, according to data from the Regional Personnel Agency (BKD). School districts and municipality's alike place a premium on having primary school teachers exhibit more self-control in the classroom. There has to be a greater push to make teachers more disciplined in their work if primary school education is to continue to improve. Data, including moral hazard techniques, are still very much present in the sector. All persons involved may feel the ill repercussions of this.

Accountability problems, misuse of authority, and laziness are all possible outcomes of moral hazard. Governments must increase their monitoring and enforcement of the law to prevent detrimental moral hazard practices. One of the many approaches to minimising or doing away with moral hazard is servant leadership. A leadership style that promotes an atmosphere of trust and accountability by having leaders prioritise the needs and welfare of their followers. It is not enough to only use a leadership style and then add incentives. Moral hazard and other risky actions are more likely to occur in a teacher who is uninspired to do their job.

It is crucial and deserving of study because, first and foremost, it may shed light on how to use motivation and servant leadership to reduce the risk of moral hazard. Secondly, the results of this research might provide directors with some good ideas for strategies that encourage employees to behave ethically and with integrity. For this study, we ask: In light of these concerns, how can servant leadership influence moral hazard and motivation directly?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Complete mastery of a "moral hazard" exists when certain individuals are more willing to take risks when they are aware that other people will inevitably suffer the consequences of their actions. When a person believes they are safe from danger because someone else will cover their expenses, this situation arises. (Sayidah, 2012). According to Scott, moral hazard occurs when one party to a business transaction or series of transactions has a better idea of how to monitor their activities than the other parties. This is an example of asymmetric information.

When stakeholders outside the organisation vest managers with power and responsibility, a moral hazard issue develops since investors are unable to monitor their actions (Musyarofah, 2008). The moral hazard concept has the potential to diminish teachers' motivation on occasion. This definition of educator applies to teachers who, due to their carelessness, experience unfavorable consequences for actions like being late or wasting class time or money. Even if it's not true, the belief that teachers should behave ethically has faded. Teachers should always behave responsibly since their students look up to them. When teachers act badly, it may have a direct impact on their students, who may start to underestimate them and lose interest in learning.

The moral hazard problem is the focus of leadership style study. An effective leadership style may reduce moral hazard by fostering an atmosphere that places a premium on transparency and personal responsibility. Furthermore, leaders should demonstrate how to properly and professionally carry out their responsibilities, which will motivate their subordinates to do the same.

The concept of servant leadership was popularized by Robert K. Greenleaf's work "The Servant as Leader" from the 1970s. (Kaltainen & Hakanen, 2022). Research and analysis by Greenleaf on servant leadership tenets should lead to the betterment of society. A leader should prioritise the needs of those under their charge, says Greenlea.

According to Melino (2016), servant leadership is more often practised in the United States than in Latin America. Furthermore, it dissects servant leadership into its constituent elements and provides an in-depth analysis of how they differ. Since the servant leadership style is gaining popularity across the world, more written material on it is needed, especially in Asia. The distinctive cultural and environmental variations in Asia call for further research on servant leadership. Global executives may get valuable insights about navigating the Americas, Latin America, and Asia by comparing and contrasting these areas.

The capacity of a leader to comprehend and respond to the feelings and viewpoints of their staff is fundamental to the achievement of any organization's goals. The principal must monitor the performance of his employees and subordinates. It is not enough for principals to only monitor teachers; they must also consistently strive to enhance their performance. A leader demonstrates servant leadership when they are brave, truthful, fair, attentive, and put their employees first. Leaders who invest in their employee's growth and development by learning about and connecting with their dreams and goals see improvements in both performance and job satisfaction (Northouse, 2021)

According to (Van Dierendonck, 2011) Being a servant leader is all about putting others before yourself. This indicates that leaders should pay more attention to their followers' needs and aspirations for the future rather than focusing on leadership itself. Leadership, therefore, is all about serving others under the guise of the leader's power. According to newly published studies (Kaltainen & Hakanen, 2022) learned that servant leadership significantly improves output, engagement, and job satisfaction.

According to Greenleaf, servant leadership is characterised by (Spears & Lawrence, 2002) A servant leader exhibits 10 traits. Namely:

- 1) Listening,
- 2) Empathy,
- 3) Healing
- 4) Familiarity,
- 5) Convincing,
- 6) Fragmentation,
- 7) Foresightful,
- 8) Serving
- 9) Dedication to personal development,
- 10) Establish a group.

In accordance with the recommendations made by (Megheirkouni, 2018) states that the three main components are leadership results, servant leader conduct, and circumstances.

A servant leader's job is supported by seven pillars: conceptualization, healing, putting followers first, helping colleagues grow, behaving ethically, empowering, and making a beneficial influence on society. A helpful definition of servant leadership was proposed by (Sendjaya, 2015) and is as follows: "a comprehensive style of leadership that involves both leaders and followers through

1. A focus on service,
2. An authenticity orientation,
3. An emphasis on relationships,
4. Moral courage, and
5. Motivation."
6. The effect that alters the course of events (Sendjaya, 2015) also noted six ways in which servant leadership impacts behaviour. Among them, we may find instances of transcendent spirituality, relationships, responsible morality, and voluntarism.

Intrinsic drive and conscientiousness are predictors of work performance. Investigations conducted by (Barrick & Mount, 1991) considers the relationship between intrinsic motivation and performance, with an emphasis on goal-setting actions, including coming up with goals on one's own, committing fully to the goal, and expecting to succeed. Everyone is born with an intrinsic desire to achieve their goals, according to one fundamental principle of goal theory (Locke & Latham, 1990) Many studies have shown that when people know what they're trying to achieve, they are more motivated, persistent, and productive.

The relationship between motivation and performance improves when goals are

- 1) Reasonable,
- 2) Acceptable,
- 3) Well-defined, and
- 4) backed by credible feedback (Bajor & Baltes, 2003).

Persuaded that goals are a great way to boost efficiency (Tubbs, 1986).

The degree to which one is motivated to work is affected by several expectations:

- 1) The expected degree of success in proportion to the effort exerted,
- 2) The anticipated payoff with respect to the degree of achievement (instrumentality)
Thirdly, the valence, or the reward's emotional worth (Fall & Patrice, 2014) claimed The internal forces that propel an individual to achieve their aspirations are called intrinsic motivation.

According to (Herzberg, 2017) Some things that motivate people include reaching objectives, getting compliments, enjoying what they do, owning up to their actions, and seeing opportunities for improvement in the future. One kind of motivation is known as "extrinsic motivation," and one example is the "hygiene factor." According to (Herzberg, 2017) as an example of anything that might function as an extrinsic motivator, we have policy and administration, quality oversight, interpersonal relationships, working circumstances, and, last but not least, remuneration. According to (Jensen, 1983) Agency theory provides a theoretical framework for analysing the dynamics of many types of connections, including those between people, groups, and organisations, as well as between principals and agents. A contractual relationship is characterised by the sharing of decision-making and task-assignment responsibilities between a principal and an agent. The primary emphasis of agency theory is on workplace incentives that increase innovation and efficiency (Meckling, 2000).

Interests can only change with more theory, but agency theory explains well how principals' and agents' interests differ. Stewardship theory may be used to describe relationships that are based on location and other behaviours. According to this theory, joint agents will put the principal's interests ahead of their own by acting counter to their self-interest (Donaldson, 2007)

METHODOLOGY

This study is a quantitative examination of correlational connections; it gathers data, examines hypotheses, and seeks answers to queries about current research topics. The researchers in this study surveyed 400 teachers from Wonosobo Regency, a district in western Japan. Participants were selected at random from all available courses using cluster random sampling. Researchers employed a questionnaire using Likert scales to get this data. The following is the structure of the research:

Picture 1: Framework of Thinking

We want to learn more about the interplay between Servant Leadership, intrinsic drive, and moral hazard by using this model. Let us imagine for the sake of argument that servant leadership does, in fact, mitigate moral hazard. The second assumption is that highly motivated individuals will be less likely to engage in moral hazard. The third point is that moral hazard may be reduced via the combined efforts of incentive and servant leadership. The following, therefore, is the study's working hypothesis:

H1: there is an influence of Servant Leadership (X1) on moral hazard (Y)

H2: there is an influence of motivation (X2) on moral hazard (Y)

H3: There is an influence of Servant Leadership (X1) and Motivation (X2) on moral hazard (Y) simultaneously

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive Test

Table 1: Data Descriptive Test

	N	MIN	MAX	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION	VARANCE
SERVANT LEADERSHIP (X1)	100	30.00	50.00	43.21	5.49250	30,168
MOTIVATION (X2)	100	28.00	50.00	43.50	6.38417	40,758
MORAL HAZARD (Y)	100	30.00	50.00	43.24	4.73994	22,467
VALID N	100					

Normality Test

Figure 2: PP Graph Plot Normality of Data

From the plot table above, it can be stated that the data obtained is normal

Multicollinearity Test

Table 2: Multicollinearity Test

	UNSTADARDIZE D		STANDARDI ZED	Q	SIG	COLLINEA RITY	VIF
	B	Std error	Beta			Tolerance	
CONSTANT	12,503	3,139		3,983	0		
SERVANT LEADERSHIP (X1)	0.368	0.064	0.426		0	0.920	1,087
MOTIVATION (X2)	0.341	0.55	0.460		0	0.920	1,087

Variables X1 and

Heteroskedasticity Test

Figure 3: Scatterplot of data

From the Scatterplot graph above, the data is said to be spread out so that heteroskedasticity does not occur.

Linearity Test

a. Moral Hazard (Y) with Servant Leadership (X1)

The significance value was found to be $0.152 > 0.05$, so there is a linear relationship

b. Moral Hazard (Y) with Motivation (X2)

The significance value was found to be $0.587 > 0.05$, so there is a linear relationship

Hypothesis testing

t test

It is known that the significance value for the influence of

It is known that the significance value for the influence of

F test

It is known that the significance value for the influence of X1 and

Regression Test

Coefficient of Determination

The R Square value is 0.501. The influence of Servant Leadership (X1) and Motivation (X2) simultaneously on Moral Hazard (Y) is 50.1% of the data representing the variables studied.

DISCUSSION AND DISCUSSION

Moral hazard is positively and significantly impacted by servant leadership. A route coefficient of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a computed t value of $6,166 > t$ table 1.98472 validate this conclusion. The coefficient indicates that there is a positive and statistically significant association between moral hazard and servant leadership. According to these studies, moral hazard is reduced as the degree of servant leadership increases. These results show that a leadership style that focuses on serving others may foster a more responsible and ethical workplace, which is a significant step towards understanding the beneficial function of servant leadership in mitigating moral hazard.

Moral hazard is positively and significantly impacted by motivation. A route coefficient of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a computed t value of $6,166 > t$ table 1.98472 validate this conclusion. This coefficient shows the positive correlation between motivation and moral hazard. According to this study, moral hazard is reduced when the amount of motivation rises. Put, when people are highly motivated, they are less likely to engage in unethical or fraudulent behaviour on the job.

Moral hazard is also affected by the combination of servant leadership and incentive. The numerical evidence for this conclusion comes from a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$ and an F-value of $49,273 > F$ table 3.09. Increased job satisfaction and dedication are the results of servant leadership's emphasis on making workers feel valued and appreciated. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation is a key factor in shaping employee actions on the job. Moral hazard is less likely to occur when workers are motivated to do a good job, which increases productivity.

The research approach is linked to agency theory and moral hazard in this study. Moral hazard is a conflict of interest that agents and principals face. Agents may use the principal's confidence for their gain, putting their interests ahead of the principal's, and this is where agency theory comes in. At the same time, moral hazard theory considers the potential dangers that arise when agents are incentivized to disregard the principal's interests and go beyond their duties. By combining these two schools of thought, this study may illuminate the effects of agent-principal conflict on institutional performance. The following step, after choosing an agent, is to direct the agent to carry out the job according to the principal's specifications. In cases when the principal is unable to keep a close eye on the agent, moral hazard, a post-contractual agency issue, may develop when the agent acts in a self-serving manner, putting the principal's interests last (Petersen, 1993). It's ethically problematic. Assume for the sake of argument that agents have a propensity to disregard major interests when given orders.

As agents, teachers knowingly engage in moral hazard behaviours prompted by both internal and external influences, and they hold the principal accountable for these acts. Both internal and external factors may impact teachers' moral hazard activities. Internal factors include the desire to produce excellent outcomes in teaching, while external factors include pressure from the institution. Also, educators believe that principals should shoulder the brunt of accountability for the moral choices their staff makes on the job.

Due to the fact that the principal has yet to learn what the teacher is like as a person and the teacher recruitment process consists solely of a written exam, there is a knowledge gap (asymmetric information) between the two parties. Principals may need help determining whether a teacher has the necessary traits and competencies due to this. To reduce the likelihood of moral hazard, it is crucial to interview or observe potential teachers in person throughout the recruiting process. This will allow for a more thorough understanding of their character and skills.

The principal gains trust in the agent's ability to regulate their behaviour via behaviour-based contracts, which eliminates the need for constant monitoring. Furthermore, principals may incentivize or penalize agents according to their performance and actions via behaviour-based contracts. Therefore, contracts based on behaviour may help principals and agents function more effectively and efficiently. Problems with identifying objective performance indicators and the possibility of agent fraud are two implementation issues with behaviour-based contracts. For this reason, principals and agents work together to establish performance metrics that accurately represent the desired outcomes. Additionally, leaders should think about how changes in field circumstances or government legislation, for example, might impact agent performance.

Positive servant leadership, on the other hand, may establish strong ties between agents and principals, which is crucial in many fields. As a result, morale in the workplace might rise, and workers will be happier in their jobs. Leaders should be aware of the nature of the work they are supervising and adjust their approach accordingly. Optimal employee performance and achievement of organizational objectives may be achieved via the impact of excellent servant leadership.

Beyond that, leaders who practise servant leadership should empathize with their staff, pay attention to what they have to say, and be there to help when they need it. Workers will feel valued and driven to do their best job if leaders and workers have a good connection, which may be achieved via this. If leaders want to see their staff grow and perform better, they need to provide them feedback that helps them do just that.

There is a strong correlation between indicators or components of empathy and the provision of motivation, making them crucial. Teachers and administrators are agents whose understanding may encourage them to refrain from engaging in moral hazard behaviours. In addition, administrators who are empathetic may better comprehend and address the challenges and concerns of their teaching staff. Having empathy allows school leaders to help teachers in the right ways, which in turn reduces the likelihood of moral hazard.

CONCLUSION

By demonstrating that moral hazard decreases as servant leadership levels rise, this study's findings corroborate the beneficial and substantial effect of servant leadership on this issue. A more responsible and ethical workplace may be achieved via a leadership style that prioritises service. On the other hand, research shows that motivation significantly impacts moral hazard,

which is the likelihood of unethical or fraudulent behaviour in the workplace, by acting as a protective factor.

This study demonstrates that moral hazard is influenced by servant leadership and incentives in tandem. The danger of moral hazard is reduced by the deployment of servant leadership, which promotes and motivates people. This, in turn, increases job satisfaction and commitment. This study describes a conflict of interest between a principal and an agent (a teacher), with the agent's propensity to disregard the principal's interests giving birth to the moral hazard dilemma. The study is also highly relevant to agency theory and moral hazard.

Positive servant leadership may foster strong connections between agents and principals, boost motivation and job satisfaction, and create a peaceful work atmosphere, as this study further demonstrates. Leaders practising servant leadership in this setting must empathise with their staff, pay attention to what they have to say, and be there for them when they need it. Understanding the agent (the instructor) and effectively managing the danger of moral hazard depends on this empathy component, which is seen as crucial in reducing moral hazard activities.

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